

Azerbaijani validation of the High-School Satisfaction Scale: Investigating within the context of education and psychological environment

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Abstract

This article presents a comprehensive examination of the adaptation of the High-School Satisfaction Scale (H-Sat Scale) into the Azerbaijani language. In this extensive study, involving a large sample of 1894 adolescents, aged 10 to 16, we validated the H-Sat Scale through confirmatory factor analysis. Various reliability measures substantiated the commendable internal consistency of the H-Sat Scale. The study also encompassed correlation analyses, shedding light on the intricate relationships between the H-Sat Scale and critical variables such as psychological distress, academic self-efficacy, and life satisfaction. We conducted an evaluation to determine whether the H-Sat Scale could predict academic self-efficacy, psychological distress, and life satisfaction. Lastly, findings revealed that academic self-efficacy played a mediating role in influencing high school satisfaction by way of life satisfaction and psychological distress. This extensive inquiry into high school satisfaction among adolescents offers profound insights into its individual and societal implications, providing valuable perspectives on a phenomenon that has grown in significance within the social, psychological and educational contexts.

Keywords: High school satisfaction; psychological distress; life satisfaction; scale adaptation

INTRODUCTION

Research on the health of adolescents has focused primarily on negative behaviors associated with negative outcomes, but more recent literature focuses on protective factors (Borraccino, 2015). During recent decades, many studies have adopted the perspective of improving the quality of life and have focused on identifying factors that are likely to increase human well-being. Adolescents' psychological health is an issue at both the individual and societal levels, as understanding the mental health needs of adolescents is key to not only realizing their potential, but also contributing to the development of our society (Flisher, 2015).

In the studies conducted, the students' school satisfaction was studied as a direct antecedent element of other educational results. Student satisfaction has been found to partially or fully mediate the effect of educational programs on academic achievement. In other words, lack of school satisfaction can hinder students' learning and therefore needs to be prevented in advance (Chang & Smith, 2008; Choi & Jun, 2011; Kim, 2019). Schools are responsible for the social and personal development of students, in other words, the development of the student as a person (Marks, 1998). It is known that a supportive school environment promotes student well-being, allows students to realize their potential, and promotes positive attitudes toward social engagement (Hunt-Sartori, 2007). These functions of schools, which are of individual and social importance, also reveal the need for quality in the education system. Student satisfaction is also an indicator of the quality of services provided, the school's ability to respond to students' needs, teaching effectiveness, assessment skills, and students' development (Gruber et al., 2010). Meanwhile, some scholars have argued that student satisfaction is important, and its relationships with other variables only emphasize its importance (Noddings, 2003; Zullig et al., 2011). Since the school environment is the place where adolescents spend most of their time, it has both positive and negative effects on their health-related behaviors by shaping behavioral patterns. Promoting improved mental health leads to a better life for the student and better performance in society (Becker et al., 2019; Fazel & Kohrt, 2019).

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Received : 1 October 2023

Accepted : 14 December 2023

Online Published : 29 December 2023

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<https://www.journalser.com>

Cite this article as: Rustamov, E., Zalova Nuriyeva, U., Rustamova, N., Allahverdiyeva, M., & Abbasov, T. (2023). Azerbaijani validation of the High-School Satisfaction Scale: Investigating within the context of education and psychological environment. *Journal of Social and Educational Research*, 2(2), 33-40.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10440992>

Schools should be evaluated in a broader sense, that is, not only on the academic outcome of students but also on non-academic outcomes such as their emotional and psychological well-being (Huebner & McCullough, 2000; Huebner et al., 2009; Torres-Zapata et al., 2022).

The studies conducted highlight the paucity of research on school satisfaction in recent years and in this regard, Huebner and Gilman assert that "school-related affective variables (e.g., school satisfaction) have been neglected and little studied, even if they are directly and/or indirectly related to academic success" (Huebner & Gilman, 2006). It should also be emphasized that research-focused studies examining adolescent well-being tend to focus more on the effects of family and individual characteristics, ignoring the impact of the amount or quality of time spent in school on the student's personality, roles, and life (Wong & Siu, 2017; Huebner, 2001). Research shows that school satisfaction is a very important variable because it is associated with learning, behavior, truancy, absenteeism, teacher-student relationships, and social environments, leading to positive changes in behavior (Konu & Rimpelä, 2002; Johnson et al., 2022). Similarly, school satisfaction includes subjective or student-perceived indicators such as an overall evaluation of students' overall school experiences. Therefore, measures of school satisfaction are necessary because they allow the assessment of students in specific areas of the school.

School satisfaction can be viewed as a cognitive-affective assessment of satisfaction with the school life experience in a general sense (Wong & Siu, 2017). Many studies suggest that school satisfaction is a multidimensional concept that depends on many factors: psychological, environmental, and behavioral (Lodi et al., 2019). Many articles focusing on the analysis of the relationship between positive psychology and school satisfaction have found that school well-being and satisfaction are determined by a number of positive feelings and characteristics: gratitude, hope, optimism, courage, and career adjustment (Ginevra et al., 2018; Hirschi, 2009). Research investigating the factors affecting school satisfaction and the student's general well-being level revealed that positive relationships between people reduce the psychosocial stress of adolescents and improve subjective well-being, as it is a concept closely related to school satisfaction (DuBois & Silverthorn, 2005). A positive school climate can prevent adolescents from engaging in risky behaviors, as parent-family and school relationships, which have a leading position in a person's life, are protective factors to prevent risky behaviors (Freeman, 2011).

It is also important to note that the influence of social and environmental variables - positive peer relationships, supportive teacher behavior, school climate, support from parents, teachers, and classmates - on school satisfaction has also been confirmed in numerous studies (DeSantis, 2006; Epstein, 1981; Wong & Siu, 2017). Zullig, Huebner, and Patton (2011) investigated the environmental factors related to adolescents' satisfaction and school experience and found that the aforementioned factors related to school climate have a great importance in terms of progress in a positive direction and

the prevention of factors that cause a decrease in school satisfaction. Interpersonal support has been found to be the strongest predictor of school satisfaction (Ito & Smith, 2006), and Lester and Cross also highlighted that peer support in high school is the most important protective factor for mental well-being (Lester & Cross, 2015).

The study and measurement of students' school satisfaction depend on the development of standardized measurement models and tools that are linguistically, metrically, and conceptually equivalent (Lodi et al., 2019). In this regard, the adaptation of this scale in Azerbaijan could greatly contribute to the development of children's positive attitudes toward school, career plans, and relevant issues. The value of the scale is not limited to taking measures related to the overall appearance and content of school satisfaction (relationships, study habits, school environment), but it also encompasses the students' satisfaction with their career plans and study goals through the lens of the school and the study program as well as with the knowledge and competence they acquire (Lodi et al., 2019).

Since the High School Satisfaction scale is a new scale, it has so far been applied to determine the attitudes and tendencies of Spanish and Peruvian adolescents toward school (Gonzalez-Valdivia et al., 2022), and the psychometric properties of the scale have been investigated. Translation of the High School Satisfaction Scale into the Azerbaijani language and examination of its psychometric properties is much needed to form the basis of evidence-driven mental health policies, prevention and intervention strategies.

METHOD

Participants and procedure

The study comprised a cohort of 1894 adolescents aged between 11 and 16 years (mean age = 12.78 years, standard deviation = 1.58). Among this cohort, 1094 individuals identified as female, constituting 57.8% of the total, while 800 participants were male, representing 42.2% of the sample. Regarding their interactions with peers within the school environment, a significant proportion of the participants expressed contentment, with 65.4% reporting satisfaction. In contrast, 16.7% conveyed a sense of partial satisfaction, while 17.9% indicated dissatisfaction with their peer relationships. In terms of their rapport with teachers, a majority of the participants reported a positive sentiment, with 66.8% indicating satisfaction. A portion, 15.9%, reported a state of partial satisfaction, while 17.2% conveyed dissatisfaction with their teacher relationships.

Data collection was executed using a web-based survey form, which was made accessible to the participants with the assistance of school psychologists. The selection of schools for participation in this research followed the convenience sampling method, affording the research team the advantage of selecting a sample that was easily accessible and suitable for the study's objectives. School psychologists played an integral role in recruiting adolescents from their respective educational

institutions and disseminated the prepared online survey links to the participants. The commencement of the online survey was prefaced by a clear articulation of the study's objectives, and informed consent was appropriately secured from all participants. Following this, the survey initiated with a section dedicated to collecting personal information, followed by the inclusion of the assessment scales employed in the study. It is noteworthy that the study did not encounter any instances of missing data, as the online survey system did not permit incomplete responses.

Ethic

Ethical considerations were paramount throughout the research endeavor. The study adhered to the ethical principles delineated in the Helsinki Declaration. Prior to the commencement of the study, the Ethics Council of the Psychology Scientific Research Institute granted ethical approval.

Measures

High School Satisfaction Scale (H-Sat Scale) was developed by Lodi et al. (2019). The scale is composed of 20 items (e.g., I am satisfied with taking this school). Items assess school satisfaction using the 5-point Likert scale (1=not at all and 5 = completely). The High-school satisfaction scale consists of five dimensions of school satisfaction: appropriateness of choice (CH), quality of school services (SE), relationships with classmates (RE), effectiveness of study habits (ST) and usefulness for a future career (CA). In the present study internal consistency of this scale ranges between 0.85-0.91.

Satisfaction with Life Scale (SWLS) was developed by Diener, et al. (1985). The SWLS is a short scale and contains 5 items (e.g., "So far I have gotten the important things I want in life") to assess satisfaction with one's life with a 7-point Likert scale (from 1- "strongly disagree" to 7- "strongly agree"). The lower scores indicated lower satisfaction with life. Analysis of the reliability presents that the internal consistency of Cronbach's alpha is .74. for SWLS.

Children and Adolescents Psychological Distress Scale (CAPDS-10) - was designed by De Stefano (2022). CAPDS-10 contains 10 items (e.g., "I have disobeyed or I have opposed my parents"). CAPDS-10 assesses distress over the most recent 2-week period using a 4-point Likert scale (from 0-"absolutely not" to 3-"almost every day"). CAPDS-10 was divided into four dimensions: Depression (Items 1–3), Anxiety (Items 4–6), Somatic Complaints (Item 7), and Aggressive Behavior (Items 8–10). Reliability considered satisfactory, Cronbach's alpha internal consistency coefficient of CAPDS-10 is .86.

The Academic Self-Efficacy Scale is unidimensional which was designed by Jerusalem and Schwarzer (1995) to determine adolescents' sense of academic self-efficacy. The scale was composed of 7 items ("I know very well what I have to do to get a high grade", "I feel comfortable in the exam because I believe in my knowledge"). Items are rated on a 5-point Likert-

type (from 1-"True for me" to 5-"False for me") measurement tool. Cronbach's alpha of the scale was found .87.

The translation process

The translation process adhered to a standardized protocol, as outlined by Beaton et al. (2000). Initially, two bilingual translators independently translated the original English version of the High-School Satisfaction Scale (H-Sat Scale) into Azerbaijani. Subsequently, the two translations were meticulously compared, and any disparities were subjected to discussion and resolution through consensus. A committee, composed of both translators and the research team, conducted a thorough review of the translated version, making necessary revisions to ensure the cultural appropriateness and comprehensibility of the items. The refined Azerbaijani version was then subjected to back-translation into English, a task performed by another bilingual translator who was kept unaware of the original rendition. The back-translated version was subsequently compared to the original text, with any discrepancies duly addressed and resolved. This meticulous process ultimately culminated in the production of the final Azerbaijani iteration of the H-Sat Scale, which was subsequently subjected to psychometric testing.

Data analysis

The present investigation sought to assess the psychometric properties of the H-Sat Scale, encompassing its structural validity, reliability, criterion-related validity, and predictive validity. In evaluating structural validity, Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA) was employed, utilizing maximum likelihood estimation. Particular attention was given to scrutinizing a range of goodness-of-fit indices, which encompassed the chi-square (χ^2) to degree of freedom (df) ratio, the Comparative Fit Index (CFI), the Normed Fit Index (NFI), the Incremental Fit Index (IFI), Tucker Lewis Index (TLI), the Standardized Root Mean Square Residuals (SRMR), and the Root Mean Square Error of Approximation (RMSEA). The internal consistency of the scale was assessed employing Cronbach's α , McDonald's omega, and Guttman's lambda coefficients.

To assess criterion-related validity, the study investigated the associations between scores on the H-Sat Scale and various psychological constructs, including adolescents' psychological distress, life satisfaction, and academic self-efficacy, through correlational analysis. Lastly, a mediation model was tested using the PROCESS macro (model 4; Hayes, 2018) to probe into whether the relationship between high school satisfaction, as measured by the H-Sat Scale, and distress/life satisfaction was mediated by levels of academic self-efficacy.

RESULTS

The structural validity assessment of the Azerbaijani H-Sat Scale revealed a robust five-factor structure [appropriateness of choice (CH), quality of school services (SE), relationships with classmates (RE), effectiveness of study habits (ST) and

Figure 1. Structure validity of the Azerbaijani H-Sat Scale CFA with standardized estimates

usefulness for a future career (CA)], supported by compelling evidence. This was underscored by the presence of significant factor loadings for all items on the Azerbaijani H-Sat Scale (see Figure 1). The statistical fit indices further substantiated the adequacy of the model, with $\chi^2(160, N = 1894) = 2153.20, p < .001$, indicating statistical significance. Additionally, the model demonstrated excellent fit across various goodness-of-fit indices, including CFI = 0.935, NFI = 0.931, IFI = 0.936, TLI = 0.923, SRMR = 0.060, and RMSEA = 0.081. Moreover, it is worth noting that the four factors included in the model exhibited significant associations with each other, adding further support to the structural validity of the H-Sat Scale.

The internal consistency reliability of the scale was thoroughly assessed through the application of three distinct coefficients: Cronbach's alpha, McDonald's omega, and Guttman's lambda. The obtained results were consistently indicative of strong reliability. Specifically, the Cronbach's alpha coefficient yielded a value of .960, underscoring the scale's commendable reliability. Additionally, the McDonald's omega coefficient, which also serves as a reliable measure, produced a value of .960. Furthermore, the Guttman's lambda coefficient yielded a

value of .968, affirming that the items within the scale effectively gauge the same underlying construct. Collectively, these outcomes provide robust evidence attesting to the very good reliability of the H-Sat Scale (see Table 1).

Table 1. Reliability coefficients for H-Sat Scale

Reliability	CH	SE	RE	ST	CA	Total
Cronbach α	.905	.850	.866	.853	.923	.960
McDonald ω	.905	.854	.867	.856	.927	.960
Guttman λ_6	.883	.815	.838	.816	.908	.968

Note. CH appropriateness of choice; SE quality of school services; RE relationships with classmates; ST effectiveness of study habits; CA usefulness for a future career

In order to establish the criterion-related validity of the five factors within the H-Sat Scale, namely appropriateness of choice (CH), quality of school services (SE), relationships with classmates (RE), effectiveness of study habits (ST), and usefulness for a future career (CA), the study employed three distinct measures: The Child and Adolescent Psychological Distress Scale, the Satisfaction with Life Scale, and the Academic Self-Efficacy Scale, as delineated in Table 2.

Table 2. Criterion-related validity of the H-Sat Scale

Variable	Psychological distress	Life satisfaction	Academic self-efficacy
Appropriateness of choice	-.444**	.376**	.435**
Quality of school services	-.401**	.341**	.384**
Relationships with classmates	-.404**	.354**	.372**
Effectiveness of study habits	-.451**	.391**	.578**
Usefulness for a future career	-.422**	.358**	.461**
High school satisfaction	-.483**	.414**	.506**

Note. ** $p < .001$

Figure 2. Predictive validity of high school satisfaction

Figure 3. Predictive validity of high school satisfaction

It is noteworthy that all correlation analyses yielded statistically significant results ($p < .001$). Consistent with expectations, the factors of high school satisfaction exhibited negative correlations with psychological distress (ranged from $r = -.483$ to $-.401$). Conversely, these factors displayed positive correlations with measures of life satisfaction (ranged from $r = .341$ to $.414$) and academic self-efficacy (ranged from $r = .372$ to $.578$). Furthermore, the broader construct of high school satisfaction demonstrated negative correlations with psychological distress ($r = -.483$), while concurrently displaying positive correlations with measures of life satisfaction ($r = .414$) and academic self-efficacy ($r = .506$). These findings underscore the criterion-related validity of the Azerbaijani version of the H-Sat Scale.

The analysis also encompassed an examination of whether academic self-efficacy played a mediating role in the relationship between high school satisfaction and psychological distress, as illustrated in Figure 2. The mediation effect was scrutinized via bootstrap analyses, revealing that academic self-efficacy indeed acted as a mediator in the relationship between high school satisfaction and life satisfaction (Bootstrap coefficient = $.025$, 95% CI = $.014 - .037$). Furthermore, the direct impact of high school satisfaction on academic self-efficacy was deemed statistically significant ($\beta = 0.114$, $p < 0.001$), underscoring the direct link between these variables. Similarly, the direct effect of academic self-efficacy on life satisfaction was also found to be significant ($\beta = 0.221$, $p < 0.001$), emphasizing the influence of academic self-efficacy on life satisfaction.

Additionally, employing bootstrap analyses, it was ascertained that academic self-efficacy functioned as a mediator in the relationship between high school satisfaction and psychological distress, as depicted in Figure 3 (Bootstrap coefficient = $-.038$, 95% CI = $-.047 - -.029$). These findings underscore the mediating role of academic self-efficacy in the associations between high school satisfaction and psychological distress.

DISCUSSION

Determining school satisfaction can provide important information in assessing the quality of education and teaching in schools, making inter-school comparisons, making service improvements, and predicting student dropout (Eskildsen et al., 2000; Kara & DeShields, 2004). Therefore, there is a need for a unique assessment tool to measure students' school satisfaction, which affects both school and diverse spheres of daily life. A High-school Satisfaction Scale (H-Sat) is a tool used worldwide. It has been adapted to different languages, and its validity and reliability have been previously investigated. This research evaluated the psychometric characteristics of students in Azerbaijani schools. For this purpose, research was conducted, and specific results were obtained. The primary purpose of the study is to adapt the H-Sat test to the Azerbaijani language, to evaluate its validity and reliability, and at the same time to investigate the relationship of the H-Sat Azerbaijani version with self-efficacy, student-teacher relationship, and well-being.

The research aimed to test the psychometric properties of the H-Sat scale, a new scale to measure. The obtained psychometric results of the study in the version adapted to the Azerbaijani language supported the original version of the method and showed that the 20 items of H-Sat are included in the five-factor structure: (a) appropriateness of choice, (b) quality of school services, (c) relationships with classmates, (d) effectiveness of study habits, and (e) usefulness for a future career (Lodi et al., 2019). Furthermore, the scale was adapted for high school-level satisfaction based on CSS validity and college satisfaction in a multidimensional perspective. The obtained results showed good psychometric properties regarding internal consistency and reliability.

High-school satisfaction scale (20 items) was psychometrically tested with different methods and samples. Various analyzes were conducted to reveal the internal consistency of the High-school satisfaction scale. When reviewing the results of the study, when analyzing the items of the school satisfaction scale, it was found that the reliability level was above 0.70 for the total score. Nunnally and Bernstein noted that Cronbach's alpha above 0.70 is acceptable (Nunnally & Bernstein, 1994). McDonald's omega and Gutmann's Lambda analyses were also performed during the internal consistency of items to check reliability. In this study, Cronbach's alpha was determined as 0.85-0.91, McDonald's omega 0.85-0.93, and Gutmann's lambda 0.82-0.90.

The Satisfaction with Life Scale (SWLS), the Child and Adolescent Psychological Distress Scale, and the Academic Self-Efficacy Scale were used to ensure the school satisfaction

scale's conformity reliability and criterion-related validity. In the next stage, Pearson's correlation coefficient was used to check the correlation between these scales and the subgroups of the High-school Satisfaction Scale mentioned above. As a result, it was found that the life satisfaction of students who are satisfied with the level of education in the school they attended and its usefulness for their future career is higher (Alzahrani et al., 2018), the level of distress of students who have a better relationship with their classmates is lower, and the level of their well-being is higher (Ruvalcaba-Romero et al., 2018; Plazas et al., 2010). Also, it was found that there is a positive correlation between the students' satisfaction with the school they chose and the indicators of the self-efficacy scale (Petruzzellis & Romanazzi, 2010) and a negative correlation with the distress scale.

Predictive validity of the High-school Satisfaction Scale showed that school satisfaction significantly predicts academic success and general well-being during adolescence (Martin et al., 2008). In addition, students who report higher school satisfaction have higher levels of life satisfaction and psychological well-being, as well as lower levels of depressive symptoms and other adverse outcomes (Suldo et al., 2008). However, it is essential to note that the relationship between these constructs can be complex and bidirectional. For example, individuals who experience high levels of stress or dissatisfaction in the school environment may be more likely to have low levels of life satisfaction and psychological well-being (Diener et al., 2010). In addition, individuals who report high levels of life satisfaction and psychological well-being may also be more likely to perceive the school environment positively. Overall, the relationship between life satisfaction, psychological well-being, and school satisfaction suggests that these constructs are all significant predictors of an individual's overall subjective well-being.

Limitation

In our research, extensive, wide-scale, and comprehensive results were obtained. However, there are certain limitations in our study. The survey was conducted online, and considering the age range of the studied groups, it has yet to be fully known to what extent the questions were correctly understood and answered. For example, the research did not include all the factors contributing to an individual's high-school experience, such as out-of-school activities or personal issues beyond school life. In addition, it may not be equally valid and reliable in different cultural or socioeconomic contexts, as other populations may have different expectations or experiences of high school. Despite these limitations, the research can provide helpful direction for future studies.

Conclusion

The findings of this study indicate that a scale is a reliable tool for measuring school satisfaction in Azerbaijani schools despite its limitations. The results will help professionals deal with school problems by evaluating the quality of education and teaching in schools, making inter-school comparisons, improving services, and predicting student absenteeism in

Azerbaijani schools. Additionally, the findings will be helpful for educators, policymakers, and researchers interested in understanding and enhancing the quality of education and teaching in Azerbaijani schools.

Funding: This article has been supported by Ministry of Science and Education Republic of Azerbaijan.

Conflict of Interest: No conflict of interest exists for this manuscript for any of the authors.

Availability of Data and Material: Data will be available on request.

Pre-registration Statement: This study was not pre-registered.

Ethical Approval: The study was performed in accordance with the ethical standards laid down in the 1964 Declaration of Helsinki and its following updates.

Consent to Participate: Informed consent was obtained from all the individual participants that were included in the study.

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